

**FOSTERING COLLABORATION OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES AND STAKEHOLDERS IN
EUROPE AND LATIN AMERICA TOWARDS CLIMATE-RESILIENT PV SYSTEMS:
THE CACTUS PROJECT**

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ABSTRACT: The CACTUS project is an international initiative fostering collaboration between European (EU) and Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) research infrastructures (RIs) to enhance photovoltaic (PV) performance, reliability, and sustainability across diverse climatic conditions. Many high solar potential regions, such as LAC, lack dedicated research facilities for long-term PV performance evaluation, while European RIs require broader climate validation. CACTUS bridges this gap by integrating world-class RIs, expertise, and standardized methodologies for testing PV systems under real-world environmental stressors. The project employs a multidisciplinary approach that combines experimental field studies, advanced material characterization, and predictive modeling. Key areas of research include degradation mechanisms in extreme climates, harmonization of testing protocols, and development of predictive maintenance strategies. Leveraging state-of-the-art facilities such as ESFRI landmarks (ILL & ESRF) and EU-SOLARIS, CACTUS also explores novel PV materials and architectures, ensuring the transferability of research outcomes across global PV markets. Recent activities have focused on field studies in the Atacama Desert, where researchers are evaluating soiling measurement methodologies to assess dust accumulation and its impact on PV performance. Additionally, synchrotron-aided characterization techniques are being explored to analyze PV degradation mechanisms at the microscopic level. These early results provide promising insights into climate-specific PV behavior. The project's structured two-year implementation plan includes RI optimization, collaborative field studies, methodology standardization, and knowledge dissemination. By fostering international cooperation, CACTUS aims to deliver transformative advancements in climate-resilient solar energy deployment, enhancing durability, efficiency, and sustainability in the global PV sector.

Keywords: *PV systems; EU-LAC collaboration; research infrastructures; climate-specific PV O&M.*

1 INTRODUCTION: CONTEXT and AIM

The performance and long-term viability of photovoltaic (PV) technology are highly dependent on environmental conditions, yet current research and testing infrastructures are often limited in their ability to assess PV systems under diverse climatic stressors. Many regions with high solar potential, such as Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), lack dedicated research facilities for long-term performance analysis. Conversely, European research infrastructures (RIs) have developed extensive methodologies but require broader climate validation. Addressing these gaps necessitates an international and interdisciplinary approach.

The CACTUS project emerges as a response to this need, fostering a bi-regional collaboration between Europe (EU) and LAC. The initiative brings together world-class

RIs, scientific expertise, and technological capabilities to develop a sustainable ecosystem for PV research. This collaboration enables the exchange of methodologies, data, and best practices to improve the performance, reliability, and sustainability of PV technologies across different environmental conditions (Fig. 1). By building on existing RIs and establishing new synergies, CACTUS will provide tools to facilitate the deployment of solar energy in an efficient and climate-resilient manner.

The primary objective of CACTUS is to advance the scientific understanding of PV systems' long-term behavior in different climates by improving testing infrastructures and developing standardized methodologies. This effort is crucial for optimizing PV performance, enhancing system bankability, and ensuring widespread social acceptance of solar technologies.

Figure 1: Geographic distribution of RIs involved in CACTUS and their respective climate zones per Köppen classification

2 APPROACH

CACTUS employs an integrative methodology combining experimental field studies, advanced material characterization, and predictive modeling. The project’s six work packages (WPs) encompass a comprehensive approach, addressing RI enhancement, knowledge exchange, sustainability assessment, and policy integration (Fig. 2).

A core aspect of CACTUS is the development and enhancement of both indoor and outdoor RIs across diverse geographic locations. This enables the study of degradation mechanisms under real-world conditions such as extreme heat, high humidity, sand abrasion, and UV exposure. The project leverages world-class facilities, including ESFRI landmarks (ILL & ESRF) and EU-SOLARIS, alongside premier PV research institutions in both EU and LAC.

Beyond physical infrastructure, CACTUS aims to standardize testing protocols and data-sharing methodologies. The project will establish common frameworks for PV module degradation analysis, operational reliability assessment, and predictive maintenance strategies. This harmonization of methodologies across regions will provide robust, transferrable knowledge applicable to different PV markets. A significant scientific contribution of CACTUS lies in its exploration of novel PV materials and architectures. By characterizing performance in diverse climatic settings, the project will provide critical data to refine material selection for emerging PV technologies, such as tandem solar cells and bifacial modules. The

research outcomes will feed into industry standards and best practices for PV design and deployment. Additionally, CACTUS incorporates sustainability and circular economy principles by conducting comprehensive life-cycle assessments (LCA). These assessments will evaluate the environmental footprint of PV technologies throughout their operational lifespan, providing essential data for policymakers and stakeholders.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework of CACTUS, illustrating the interconnection between RIs, under the social-environmental-economic nexus for PV deployment.

The collaborative structure of CACTUS is pivotal to its innovation potential. By fostering exchanges between EU and LAC researchers, the project promotes skill development, knowledge transfer, and long-term partnerships. Workshops, training programs, and joint research campaigns will ensure the dissemination of best practices and accelerate innovation in PV performance optimization.

Figure 3: Outline of CACTUS activities.

3 MILESTONES and ONGOING WORK

CACTUS is expected to generate a wealth of collaborative scientific and technological outcomes towards climate-resilient PV, from design/component level to operational PV system scale (Fig. 4). One key outcome is the creation of a high-quality, long-term dataset on PV performance and degradation under real-world conditions. This dataset will serve as a foundation for developing more accurate reliability models, failure detection algorithms, and predictive maintenance

strategies. Another critical result will be the establishment of guidelines, recommendations and best practices for testing, monitoring and maintenance of PV systems in diverse climatic stress profiles and different applications. These protocols will be shared both among the participating RIs and to interested PV stakeholders, facilitating greater alignment between EU and LAC research methodologies, improving the transferability of results across regions and setting the groundwork for future updates in existing (e.g. IEC) standards.

Figure 4: Ongoing collaborative research activities in CACTUS.

The implementation plan for CACTUS is structured over a two-year period, with key milestones including:

- Optimization and interconnection of RIs to facilitate high-quality PV performance monitoring.
- Execution of collaborative field studies and laboratory-based assessments to validate degradation models.
- Development and publication of standardized methodologies for climate-specific PV evaluation.
- Knowledge dissemination through international conferences, technical workshops, and training sessions.
- Delivery of policy recommendations based on sustainability assessments and techno-economic analyses.

By strengthening collaboration between research infrastructures in different climate zones, CACTUS is set to provide transformative insights that will enhance the durability, efficiency, and sustainability of PV systems.

Currently, there are two major activities carried out by CACTUS partners, the preliminary outcomes of which are summarized in Fig. 5 and 6. In Atacama desert, an activity led by ATAMOSTEC focuses on the intercomparison of soiling measurement methodologies, in order to:

- Evaluate and compare methodologies to measure dust accumulation and assess soiling losses on PV modules in the Atacama Desert.
- Validate soiling measurement methodologies using the advanced PSDA (Atacama Solar Platform) infrastructure.
- Generate results that can be extrapolated to other regions with similar climatic conditions.

Figure 5: Overview of the employed infrastructure and preliminary results of the ongoing intercomparison of soiling measurement methodologies in Atacama Desert. The activity is led by ATAMOSTEC, involves all CACTUS partners' expertise and will carry on for at least 15 months, to shed light into seasonal, annual climate-specific effects.

Further, ESRF experts, along with CEA and ILL researchers are working on exploring and employing ESRF's unique Synchrotron-aided characterization techniques, as potential future services for advanced characterization and analysis of PV degradation mechanisms at microscopic scale. Results, so far, are very promising, suggesting that we can study in-depth not only

the native state PV modules at solar cell and sub-cell level, but also to assess and distinguish degradation patterns over time, under the influence of different climatic profiles.

Figure 6: Overview of the employed infrastructure and preliminary results of the ongoing activity led by ESRF, for advanced characterization and analysis of PV degradation mechanisms at microscopic scale, employing ESRF’s unique Synchrotron-aided testing methods.

The CACTUS project is strategically designed to bridge the critical gap between photovoltaic research advancements and industrial market requirements. A comprehensive stakeholder survey was conducted to align the project’s objectives with practical needs, identifying paramount industry concerns such as long-term reliability across diverse climatic conditions, the accurate prediction of real-world performance, and establishing climate-specific bankability assurances. Prominent technical challenges include ultraviolet-induced degradation in desert environments, humidity-driven corrosion in tropical zones, and mechanical stress from snow and ice loading in alpine climates. To evaluate the project’s capacity to address these needs, a systematic analysis of its research infrastructures was undertaken. A SWOT analysis of the project’s testing capabilities (Fig. 7) confirmed the strategic strength of its geographically distributed facilities, which provide unparalleled environmental exposure. However, the analysis also revealed significant capability gaps within the project’s scope, particularly in testing resilience to hail and high-wind impacts, a shortage of predictive maintenance tools, and the need for more affordable access mechanisms for small and medium-sized enterprises. In direct response to these industry-identified needs and infrastructural insights, the project has developed novel, climate-adaptive testing protocols.

Methodologies like the Desert Label and STROKE testing are already addressing market demand by providing more relevant and accelerated reliability assessments, thereby enabling manufacturers to develop more robust products and allowing investors to make better-informed financial decisions based on validated, climate-specific performance data.

Figure 7: Overview of the employed infrastructure and preliminary results of the ongoing activity led by ESRF, for advanced characterization and analysis of PV degradation mechanisms at microscopic scale, employing ESRF’s unique Synchrotron-aided testing methods.

4 CONCLUSIONS - OUTLOOK

The CACTUS project has established a unique bi-regional collaboration between Europe and Latin America & the Caribbean, addressing one of the most pressing challenges in photovoltaic (PV) deployment: the lack of climate-representative infrastructures and standardized methodologies for long-term performance evaluation. By interconnecting world-class research facilities,

harmonizing testing approaches, and fostering interdisciplinary knowledge exchange, CACTUS provides the foundation for advancing PV reliability studies across diverse climatic conditions. Early results from ongoing activities—such as the intercomparison of soiling methodologies in the Atacama Desert and synchrotron-aided degradation analysis at ESRF—demonstrate the project’s capacity to generate high-quality data and innovative characterization methods, both of which are

critical for bridging the gap between laboratory studies and field-relevant insights.

The project highlights that climate-specific stressors—including soiling, humidity-driven corrosion, UV degradation, and thermal cycling—require tailored testing and mitigation strategies. CACTUS directly responds to these needs by developing adaptive testing protocols, sustainability assessments, and techno-economic frameworks to ensure PV systems' durability, bankability, and social acceptance in different regions. Looking forward, key priorities include:

- expanding climate-tailored reliability assessments to encompass additional stress factors (e.g. hail, wind, and snow loads),
- integrating advanced predictive maintenance tools with real-time field data, and
- strengthening accessibility of testing infrastructures for industry stakeholders, particularly SMEs.

By aligning scientific research with market and policy needs, CACTUS not only advances the state-of-the-art in PV testing but also lays the groundwork for future updates of international standards and guidelines. Ultimately, the project is expected to deliver a lasting impact by enabling climate-resilient PV deployment, supporting the global energy transition with reliable, sustainable, and regionally adapted solar technologies.

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